

CHEMISTRY OF RARE EARTHS. PARTS VIII. UROTROPIN AND ANTI-PYRENE COMPLEXES OF THIOSULPHATES OF RARE EARTHS

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Preparation and properties of complexes of rare earth thiosulphates with urotropin and anti-pyrene have been described.

Rare earth nitrates have been known to give beautiful crystalline compounds with urotropin (Barbier and Calzolari, *Atti. R. Acad. Lincei*, 1911, v, 20, 164) and anti-pyrene (Kolbe, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1913, 83, 143). Such compounds of these weak organic bases with rare earth perchlorates, iodides and nitrites, *i.e.*, salts of weak acids, some of which (nitrites and iodides) had not been known to exist in the solid state, were isolated by Wilke-Dorfurt and Schliephake (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1928, 170, 123) and others. This may well be looked upon as a case of stabilisation by complex formation with organic molecules. All attempts to isolate rare earth thiosulphates in the solid state failed (Sarkar, *Ann. chim.*, 1927, x, 8, 239). The present author isolated several double thiosulphates of rare earths with alkali metal thiosulphates (this *Journal*, 1949, 26, 405). Investigations into formation of compounds of rare earth thiosulphates with urotropin and anti-pyrene were next undertaken. Preparation and properties of such compounds form the subject matter of the present communication.

EXPERIMENTAL

Lanthanum-urotropin Thiosulphate.—Lanthanum nitrate (5 g.)^a was dissolved in the least quantity of water, cooled, and to this was added dropwise urotropin (6 g.), also dissolved in the least quantity of cold water. The clear solution was filtered and to the filtrate was then added 3 c.c. of a saturated solution of sodium thiosulphate when lanthanum-urotropin thiosulphate separated in microcrystalline form. These crystals were filtered under suction and washed carefully with ice-cold water and recrystallised from least quantity of ice-water.

The compound is white, micro-crystalline and moderately soluble in water. It is less soluble than the corresponding nitrate. An aqueous solution of the salt decomposes on dilution slowly with separation of sulphur and gives lanthanum hydroxide on boiling. [Found: La, 26.92, 26.92; S, 18.62, 18.46; N, 16.30, 16.35. $\text{La}_2(\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)_2, 3\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4$ requires La, 26.88; S, 18.57; N 16.25 per cent].

Cerous-urotropin thiosulphate was prepared in the same way as in the above case using cerous nitrate for lanthanum nitrate. It resembles the previous compound in all respects. [Found: Ce, 27.23, 26.95; S, 18.36, 18.74; N 16.32, 16.35. $\text{Ce}_2(\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)_2, 3\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4$ requires Ce, 27.03; S, 18.53; N 16.21 per cent].

Praseodymium-urotropin thiosulphate was also prepared in an analogous way to the other two cases using praseodymium nitrate as the starting material. The compound

is light green. In all other respects it resembles the previous compounds. [Found: Pr, 27.25, 27.08; S, 18.67, 18.62; N, 16.08, 16.25. $\text{Pr}_2(\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)_3, 3\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4$ requires Pr, 27.16; S, 18.50; N, 16.20 per cent].

Lanthanum-antipyrene Thiosulphate.—To a concentrated solution of lanthanum nitrate (3 g.) was added an aqueous solution of antipyrene (5 g.). Crystals separated, if any, were dissolved in the least quantity of cold water and added dropwise. To this solution was then added dropwise a saturated solution of sodium thiosulphate when beautiful colorless crystals separated. It was filtered under suction, washed with ice-cold water twice and recrystallised from least quantity of cold water.

The compound is colorless and crystalline in nature. It is also moderately soluble in water but less so than the corresponding urotropin compound. An aqueous solution decomposes gradually in the cold but more so on heating with the separation of sulphur. The compound melts above 300° with decomposition. [Found: La, 16.25, 15.75; S, 11.24, 10.95; N, 9.46, 9.85. $\text{La}_2(\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)_3, 6\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4\text{O}$ requires La, 15.96; S, 11.02; N, 9.65 per cent].

Cerous-antipyrene thiosulphate was prepared in the same way as described in the case of the corresponding lanthanum compound, taking cerous nitrate in place of lanthanum nitrate. It resembles the lanthanum compound in almost all respects. It melts above 320° with decomposition. [Found: Ce, 16.25, 16.18; S, 11.24, 10.86; N, 9.45, 9.56. $\text{Ce}_2(\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)_3, 6\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4\text{O}$ requires Ce, 16.06; S, 11.01; N, 9.63 per cent].

Praseodymium-antipyrene thiosulphate was prepared in an analogous way to the other cases, using praseodymium nitrate. It is light green in colour, and in all other respects it resembles the previous compounds. It melts with decomposition at $320^\circ\text{--}330^\circ$. [Found: Pr, 16.26, 16.05; S, 10.95, 10.78; N, 9.82, 9.65. $\text{Pr}_2(\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)_3, 6\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4\text{O}$ requires Pr, 16.14; S, 10.82; N, 9.62 per cent].

Method of Analysis

Rare earth was estimated by the direct ignition of a weighed quantity of the salt and weighed as oxide. Sulphur was estimated as BaSO_4 after oxidation with ammoniacal hydrogen peroxide and separation of rare earth hydroxide. Nitrogen in urotropin compound was estimated by Kjeldahl's method after decomposition with concentrated sulphuric acid for several hours. Nitrogen in antipyrene compounds was estimated by Duma's method of combustion.